

ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN AREAS OF ACTIVITY OF LAW ENFORCEMENT AGENCIES

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Annotation: This article talks about the current status of community law enforcement agencies, the opinions of legal scholars in this regard..

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In our country, as in all areas, large-scale reforms were carried out in the Prevention of violations, and a unique national system was created in this direction. Prevention of offenses has become a priority not only for the general direction of the fight against crime, but also for all government agencies in the country. The methods of organizing the activities of law enforcement agencies were radically changed, in particular, it was established as the most important task of these agencies not to expose cases of violations of the law and take measures, but to ensure the premature prevention and Prevention of these cases.

Based on the content of the reforms carried out in the field of prevention of offenses, the following separate directions can be distinguished, firstly, on the improvement of the activities of the subjects of prevention of offenses and their empowerment; secondly, on the improvement of the legal framework of prevention of offenses; thirdly, on the improvement of the material and technical base of

In improving the effectiveness of the Prevention of violations, it is important to create sufficient conditions for the organization of the activities of the subjects, in particular, to provide material and technical, modern means of information and communication, to organize service rooms with all amenities, etc.

Among the subjects of prevention of violations, preventive inspectors occupy the most important place. They are charged with such tasks as maintaining public order and ensuring security in the section of neighborhoods, protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens, legitimate interests, organizing and implementing measures of general, special, individual and victimological prevention of violations.

On the basis of the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 18, 2020 "on measures to restore the socio-spiritual environment in society, further support of the neighborhood Institute and bring the system of working with family and women to a new level", the positions of preventive inspector state units were increased to 2573, their number was increased from 7302 to 9875, Today, more than 10,000 preventive inspectors serve in our republic.

Russian scientist V.N. An important aspect of Prokopenko's preventive activities, which is distinguished from the activities of any other branch of the IIO service, is the fact that it covers all areas of the IIO's activities, is complex and multifunctional[1], one can say the correct assessment given to the activities of Pilari today.

Therefore, special attention was paid to improving the activities of the preventive inspector, the process of reforms carried out in the field of prevention of violations.

In this matter, our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "it is impossible to come from a distant district and work as a preventive inspector, so we pay special attention to the issue of providing them with housing, service machines. Today, 120 of the 368 preventive inspectors have been solemnly handed over housing and motor vehicles" [2], he noted.

In fact, since the responsibility of the preventive inspector was assigned to them, there was a need to maintain public order and ensure security in the administrative territory attached by them, to carry out the Prevention of offenses, to create sufficient conditions for organizing the cooperative activities of other subjects of the Prevention of violations serving the territory in the process, in particular, other Therefore, at today's stage of reforms, special attention was paid to measures to eliminate these problems.

In our opinion, on the basis of the base of the base points, the establishment of step-by-step neighborhood Law Enforcement facilities is established, which are a structural structure at the very bottom of the internal affairs bodies, which directly carry out the activities of maintaining public order in neighborhoods and villages, prevention of violations and combating crime, as well as ensuring the safety and tranquility of citizens

Of course, while the base point differs from the neighborhood law enforcement centers in a certain activity, its organization on its basis also covers certain areas of activity assigned to them.

Currently, the social control over crime in our republic is a unique system that has its advantages in that it conditionally has the opportunity to participate directly in the provision of all these directions within the framework of its functions, taking into account the fact that punishment for crimes committed is inevitable; 3) ensuring the execution of punishment prescribed by the court. [3]

In fact, today the neighborhood law enforcement area can be considered a more unique structure that plays an important role in the organization and coordination of the Prevention of violations, which has even wider opportunities than base points.

At the same time, the neighborhood law enforcement area is equipped with modern techniques and information and communication tools, unlike the base point, where work in all directions renounces excess paperwork, the activity manifests itself as a digitized and electronic structure.

The decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 2, 2021 "on additional organizational measures to further improve the activities of the internal affairs bodies in the field of Public Security and combating crime" PQ-5050 will be of significant importance in organizing the activities of law enforcement agencies. In particular, by this decision, the regulations on the law enforcement area of the neighborhood were adopted and their status and main tasks were determined.

It should be noted that in addition to certain tasks assigned to the law enforcement agencies to the base points, the following tasks are also assigned:

1) the fact that the activities of law enforcement agencies are aimed at organizing joint work of internal affairs bodies, other state bodies and public structures in the neighborhood section;

2) the solution of the problems of the population, as well as the tasks of organizing the work of social adaptation of persons who have suffered from an offense, have anti-social behavior, committed an offense;

3) to prevent violations prematurely by performing uniform centralized electronic monitoring and monitoring, using video surveillance devices installed at the entrance and exit points of the neighborhood and other facilities in the area, etc.

The establishment of neighborhood Law Enforcement facilities is instrumental in improving the effectiveness and quality level of crime prevention. In particular, these aspects can be seen in the following, firstly, that law enforcement agencies are provided with the most modern means of Information Communication; secondly, that they carry out unified centralized electronic monitoring and monitoring; thirdly, in addition to preventive inspectors, other field services of the internal affairs bodies, the organization of activities of state bodies, National Guard bodies and public structures for the Prevention of violations, etc.

There are certain problems and disadvantages in the organization of neighborhood Law Enforcement facilities and their activities that it is impossible to achieve sufficient results in ensuring the implementation of the tasks set in this direction without eliminating them, including:

first of all, the inadmissibility of the departmental regulatory legal document of the IIV, which defines the rights and complexities of preventive inspectors for the organization of the activities of Neighborhood law enforcement agencies;

secondly, it should be noted that the majority of preventive inspectors do not have an understanding of what features they differ from the base points of the neighborhood law enforcement area, it is worth noting that in a survey on this matter, 87.4% of respondents did not know the difference, 3.2% said that the difference was in name, and 9.4;

thirdly, there is no mechanism for the non-existence of plans and reporting samples of preventive inspectors for the organization of the activities of Neighborhood law enforcement agencies in all regions of the Republic, in particular, in which areas plans are prepared and reports are submitted on their basis;

fourth, the absence of the development of a regulatory legal document, in which the specific powers of the preventive inspector are determined in determining the tasks for the territory to employees of industry service personnel and organizations, National Guard bodies involved in maintaining public order in the neighborhood law enforcement area.

fifth, paragraph 3 of Chapter 1 of the regulation "on the law enforcement area of the neighborhood" approved by Annex 1 of resolution PQ-5050 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 2, 2021 "on additional organizational measures to further improve the activities of the internal affairs bodies in the field of Public Security and combating crime", because from this definition comes the concept that 2 or 3 Law Enforcement places will be established in one, large districts and cities in the province;

Indeed, an important aspect of the organization of the activities of neighborhood law enforcement agencies is the fact that determining the conditions for their organization where and in what order remains one of the current tasks today.

Therefore, it is advisable to carry out the following measures to improve the organization of neighborhood law enforcement agencies and their activities, increase the effectiveness of their activities in the Prevention of violations:

in the regulation "on the neighborhood law enforcement area", it is necessary to clearly define what areas of law enforcement areas are organized in districts and cities, for example, in the sense that "neighborhood law enforcement areas are organized in the Central and crowded areas of urban districts" ;

accelerate the establishment of Law Enforcement facilities in existing neighborhoods in our republic;

to the process of organizing the activities of law enforcement agencies, to issue orders of internal affairs bodies for attachment on the surname, first and second name, position of personnel from other industry service personnel, in particular, investigative, operational-search, patrol-post, Road Traffic Safety, migration and citizenship clearance services and National Guard bodies;

Organization of training courses of preventive inspectors on a separate schedule without separation from service in the services of prevention of violations on the organization of activities of the neighborhood law enforcement area;

to determine to the regulation on the law enforcement area of the neighborhood about their infrastructure, in particular how many rooms they will have, what equipment and equipment they will be equipped with, what to organize around the residences.

Also, the absence of a neighborhood Law Enforcement facility requires the introduction of additional and amendments to the law, including an article defining the status of "Neighborhood law enforcement agencies", although Article 15 of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 16, 2016 contains the norm called "base points of internal affairs bodies".

The analysis of the legal literature, legislation and the practice of organizing Management shows that the principles of their activities are laid down in order to ensure that the body, institution or public structure operating in any field achieves its intended purpose and effectively carries out its duties, and, moreover, strictly follows the requirements of the norms of law and ethics. Principles serve as the basis for determining the functions, rights and obligations in the organization of the activity of the subject.

It should be noted that some of the problems that exist in the activities of base points are also encountered in the process of organizing the activities of neighborhood law enforcement agencies.

In this regard M.Z.Ziyodullaev also pointed out: "the analysis of regulatory legal acts regulating the activities of IIO TPS shows that they do not clearly define the principles of the activities of TPS and their functions for the performance of the tasks assigned. This creates certain problems in the effective and purposeful Organization of the activities of TPS, ensuring the rule of law in the process, requiring Pilar and other entities to carry out certain measures in service activities and responsibility for this, and their legal protection"[5].

It is also necessary to determine the powers and duties of senior management personnel in the organization of the activities of neighborhood law enforcement agencies.

For example, in regulatory legal acts, the mayors of the district (city) meet in person with the senior inspector of Prevention, who heads the neighborhood Law Enforcement center, take measures to solve problematic issues identified in the area regarding public safety, District (City) Councils of people's deputies hear every half year the report of the senior inspector of Prevention, who heads the neighborhood law enforcement Also, the senior inspector of prevention is the immediate head of the mask and is charged with the

responsibility of effectively organizing the day-to-day work on the maintenance of Public Order and the Prevention of violations in the neighborhood (village) [6].

If, by this rule, the senior inspector of prevention is recognized as the head of the settlement, it indicates the integrity of the governors to control its activities. However, no specific powers of the Senior Inspectors of prevention and the immediate head of preventive inspectors, officials of the internal affairs bodies responsible for organizing their activities for the Prevention of violations, in the organization, coordination and control of the activities of the neighborhood Law Enforcement facility are established.

This can be seen in the fact that the neighborhood law enforcement area has not been clarified to which official it reports to and obeys. At the same time the neighborhood requires the determination of the order of submission of Law Enforcement facilities.

In this regard, the Russian researcher Pavlovski V.V. "States that the procedures for the accountability and public control of the militia bodies before the government bodies are dual subordination, that is, subordinate to the local authorities and the Ministry of internal affairs[7].

Indeed, one way to eliminate some misunderstandings in this regard is to determine the specific powers and duties of local state authorities and internal affairs bodies on the basis of regulatory legal acts on the organization of the activities of neighborhood law enforcement agencies.

It should be noted that in increasing the effectiveness of the Prevention of violations, an important role is played by improving the activities of neighborhood law enforcement agencies, providing them with new modern techniques and information and communication tools, and organizing the work of residents and their residents in the neighborhoods of our republic.

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